

Photonic Data Storage by Electromagnetically Induced Transparency

Dissertation

**Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirement for the
degree of**

**Bachelor of Science (Hons)
in
Physics**

**By
Avirup Chakraborty
under the supervision of**

**Dr. Shrabana Chakrabarti
Department of Physics
Sister Nivedita University
Newtown, Kolkata**

Roll no. 1811107009007

July 2021

Contents

Introduction:.....	3
Theory.....	3
An Atom and its Interactions with Light:	3
Hamiltonian of the Atom:	3
Hamiltonian of the Electromagnetic Field:	4
Hamiltonian of the Dipole Interaction:	7
Hamiltonian of a three level lambda system.....	9
Eigenstates and Energy eigenvalues of the EIT Hamiltonian:	11
Dark state, Bright state and Excited states:.....	12
Langevin's equations of motion:.....	12
Susceptibility of the Lambda System:	15
Pulse propagation through EIT medium:	17
The number state representation of the N lambda atom Hamiltonian:	19
Generalized dark state and quantum memory:.....	20
Propagation of Dark Polariton Fields.....	22
Conclusion:	25
Bibliography	25

Introduction:

Electromagnetically Induced Transparency is a non-linear optical phenomenon in which one strong laser called control laser and one less strong laser called the probe laser are used to couple two hyperfine components of the ground state of the atom to the excited state. At resonance, when the lasers' frequency almost matches the energy gap between the states, the transition probabilities of the electron from the two hyperfine components of ground state to the excited state destructively interfere. In this process the electron population from the ground state do not make transition to the excited state, so the probe laser does not get absorbed and the medium gets transparent to it. This induced transparency can be utilized to drive a probe pulse inside a medium and then switching off the control laser lifting up the resonance, adiabatically. Since there will be no resonance so the transparency too would be vanished and the probe laser inside the medium will be trapped in its instantaneous state as per the adiabatic theorem, thus stored. We can again make it propagate turning on the control laser retrieving it.

Theory

An Atom and its Interactions with Light:

The atom without any interaction can thought of as an unperturbed system which is composed of the electrons and the nucleus. The interaction present in this atom are due to the Coulomb Force between the electrons themselves and between the nucleus and the electron. This is true for any level atomic system. The states can an atom be in represented by the state or basis vectors in Hilbert Space or by a linear combination of them.

The light is (as we all aware of) is a wave in the Electromagnetic Fields, and it has an energy and momentum, described by the Classical Electrodynamics. Although we are dealing with a quantum mechanical system like atom, we will be using the classical description to describe the electromagnetic waves since we assume we are dealing with electromagnetic waves with wavelengths much greater than the atomic radii. Although we can formulate it's Hamiltonian in the form of a quantum harmonic oscillator as we shall do in coming sections.

The electromagnetic field when come in contact with the atom, the electron and the nucleus experience a coulomb force due to the external electric field and the nucleus' wave function get elongated towards the direction of the electric field and the electron wave function gets displaced in the opposite direction forming a dipole. This is called dipole interaction.

Hamiltonian of the Atom:

As we have declared the atom without any external fields to interact with will have Coulomb interaction of each electron with the other electron and the nucleus. The total interaction summed up represent a scalar potential which influences the electron. Therefore, the potential can be given by

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left(- \sum_{j=1}^Z \frac{e}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_j|} + \frac{Ze}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}|} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where \mathbf{r} , \mathbf{r}_j , \mathbf{R} are the position vectors of the point at which potential is calculated, that of the jth electron and that of the nucleus respectively.

So the total energy of the atom is the kinetic energy of the electrons and potential energy due to the scalar potential $\phi(\mathbf{r})$. Therefore, the Hamiltonian can be given by as

$$\widehat{H}_A = \sum_{j=1}^Z \frac{\widehat{\mathbf{p}}_j^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2} \int \rho \phi(\mathbf{r}) dV \quad (2)$$

Where ρ is the total electron charge density of the atom, and $\widehat{\mathbf{p}}_j$ is the momentum operator of jth electron.

Now in a N-energy state atom when the Hamiltonian acts upon ith atomic state with frequency ω_i it must satisfy the following:

$$\widehat{H}_A|i\rangle = \hbar\omega_i|i\rangle$$

Obtaining inner product of both side by $\langle j|$ we get,

$$\langle j|\widehat{H}_A|i\rangle = \langle j|\hbar\omega_i|i\rangle$$

$$\langle j|\widehat{H}_A|i\rangle = \hbar\omega_i|i\rangle\langle j| = \hbar\omega_i\delta_{ij}$$

$$\widehat{H}_A = \langle i|\widehat{H}_A|i\rangle = \hbar\omega_i|i\rangle\langle i| = \hbar\omega_i\widehat{\sigma}_{ii}$$

$$\widehat{H}_A = \hbar\omega_i\widehat{\sigma}_{ii} \quad (3)$$

where $\widehat{\sigma}_{ii} = |i\rangle\langle i|$ is called the density operator or projection operator which gives us the probability of the atom to be in a particular state.

Hamiltonian of the Electromagnetic Field:

The total energy of the electromagnetic is given by

$$E_{EM} = \frac{1}{2} \int (\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{B}^2) dV \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the Hamiltonian of the EM field is given in the same exact form by

$$H_F = \frac{1}{2} \int (\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{B}^2) dV \quad (5)$$

We know from classical electrodynamics that the electric field and the magnetic field can be represented in terms of the magnetic vector potential \mathbf{A} and scalar potential ϕ in the following

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi + \frac{\partial\mathbf{A}}{\partial t} \quad \mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (6)$$

Choosing Scalar Potential ϕ to be zero we get

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial\mathbf{A}}{\partial t} \quad \mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (7)$$

By the Maxwell Equation in a charge free region we know

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \epsilon_0\mu_0 \frac{\partial\mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Substituting for \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{B} from previous equations we get

$$\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}) = \epsilon_0\mu_0 \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{A}}{\partial t} \right)}{\partial t} \quad \frac{\partial \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\nabla(\nabla\mathbf{A}) - \nabla^2\mathbf{A} = \varepsilon_0\mu_0 \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{A}}{\partial t^2} \quad \nabla\mathbf{A} = \text{constant, so } \nabla(\nabla\mathbf{A}) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\nabla^2\mathbf{A} = -\varepsilon_0\mu_0 \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{A}}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\mathbf{A}}{\partial t^2} \quad (11)$$

Now this is a wave equation which the vector potential satisfies in free space.

The solution of \mathbf{A} is given by separable variables in t and \mathbf{r} as

$$\mathbf{A} = \sum_m \mathbf{c}(\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) + \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})) \quad (12)$$

where the $\alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})$ are the complex conjugates

Substituting this solution in the wave equation omitting the constant we get

$$\nabla^2(\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) + \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})) = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2(\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) + \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}))}{\partial t^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha_m(t)\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) + \alpha_m^*(t)\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m(t)}{\partial t^2}\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m^*(t)}{\partial t^2}\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) \quad (14)$$

Equating the main solution terms $\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})$ and its complex conjugates $\alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})$ on both the sides we get a separable equation and its complex conjugate equation, both of them having identical forms of solution. So we need to solve the main part only

$$\alpha_m(t)\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m(t)}{\partial t^2}\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) \quad (15)$$

Dividing throughout by $\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})$ & taking separation constant we get

$$\frac{\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})}{\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})} = \frac{-\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m(t)}{\partial t^2}}{\alpha_m(t)} = k_m^2 \quad (16)$$

$$\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) = k_m^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) \quad \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m(t)}{\partial t^2} = -k_m^2\alpha_m(t) \quad \text{taking } k_m^2c^2 = \omega_m^2 \quad (17)$$

$$\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) = -k_m^2\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) \quad \frac{\partial^2\alpha_m(t)}{\partial t^2} = \omega_m^2\alpha_m(t) \quad (18)$$

The solution is given by the of course $\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) = ce^{ik_m\mathbf{r}}$ $\alpha_m(t) = de^{-i\omega_m t}$

So the vector potential is represented as

$$\mathbf{A} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_m}} (\alpha_m(0)e^{i(k_m\mathbf{r}-\omega_m t)} + \alpha_m^*(0)e^{-i(k_m\mathbf{r}-\omega_m t)}) \quad (19)$$

where the $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_m}}$ is the required constant inserted for simplicity, and $\alpha_m(0)$ is the initial value. Now electric and magnetic fields can also be written in this form.

$$\mathbf{E} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_m}} \frac{\partial(\alpha_m(0)e^{i(k_m\mathbf{r}-\omega_m t)} + \alpha_m^*(0)e^{-i(k_m\mathbf{r}-\omega_m t)})}{\partial t}$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_m}} i\omega_m(\alpha_m(0)e^{i(k_m r - \omega_m t)} - \alpha_m^*(0)e^{-i(k_m r - \omega_m t)})$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_m}{2\varepsilon_0}} i(\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) - \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})) \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\omega_m\varepsilon_0}} \nabla \times (\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) + \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r})) \quad (21)$$

Now we know that $\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})$ is an orthogonal function so it will satisfy the condition

$$\int \mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{u}_n(\mathbf{r}) dV = \delta_{mn} \quad (22)$$

Let $\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) = i\mathbf{k}_m \mathbf{u}'_m$ since $\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})$ is orthogonal \mathbf{u}'_m is also orthogonal.

So, the volume integrals of modulus square of the electric and magnetic fields can be written as (summations over m is implied)

$$\int \mathbf{E}^2 dV = -\sqrt{\frac{\omega_m}{2\varepsilon_0}} \sqrt{\frac{\omega_m}{2\varepsilon_0}} \int (\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) - \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}))(\alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) - \alpha_m(t)\mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r})) dV$$

$$\int \mathbf{E}^2 dV = -\frac{\omega_m}{2\varepsilon_0} (\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t) - 2(\alpha_m(t)^2 + \alpha_m^*(t)^2)) \quad (23)$$

by applying the orthogonality condition:

$$\int \mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{u}_m(\mathbf{r}) dV = 1 \quad (24)$$

$$\int \mathbf{B}^2 dV = -\sqrt{\frac{1}{2\omega_m\varepsilon_0}} \int (\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{k}_m \mathbf{u}'_m + \alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{k}_m \mathbf{u}'_m^*)(\alpha_m^*(t)\mathbf{k}_m \mathbf{u}'_m^* + (\alpha_m(t)\mathbf{k}_m \mathbf{u}'_m)) dV$$

by applying the orthogonality condition:

$$\int \mathbf{u}_m^*(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{u}'_m(\mathbf{r}) dV = 1$$

$$\int \mathbf{B}^2 dV = -\frac{k_m^2}{2\omega_m\varepsilon_0} (\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t) + 2(\alpha_m(t)^2 + \alpha_m^*(t)^2))$$

$$\int \mathbf{B}^2 dV = -\frac{\mu_0\omega_m}{2} (\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t) + 2(\alpha_m(t)^2 + \alpha_m^*(t)^2)) \quad (28)$$

Now we can represent the Hamiltonian of EM fields in terms of the time varying part of the vector potential \mathbf{A}

$$H_F = \frac{1}{2} \int (\varepsilon_0 \mathbf{E}^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{B}^2) dV$$

$$H_F = \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon_0 \int \mathbf{E}^2 dV + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int \mathbf{B}^2 dV)$$

$$H_F = \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon_0 \left(-\frac{\omega_m}{2\epsilon_0} (\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t) - 2(\alpha_m(t)^2 + \alpha_m^*(t)^2)) \right) + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(-\frac{\mu_0\omega_m}{2} (\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t) + 2(\alpha_m(t)^2 + \alpha_m^*(t)^2)) \right) \right) \quad (29)$$

Simplifying we get $H_F = \omega_m(\alpha_m^*(t)\alpha_m(t) + \alpha_m(t)\alpha_m^*(t))$ summed over all m. Now we can represent the same in terms of the quantum harmonic oscillator which will be important for us in later discussion about quantum memory as representing the fields in this way give us tremendous power of formulation. Since $\alpha_m(t)$ is a complex number we can represent in terms of real and imaginary parts likewise:

$$\alpha_m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\omega_m}} (\omega_m q_m + i p_m) \quad \alpha_m^* = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\omega_m}} (\omega_m q_m - i p_m) \quad (30)$$

Representing the field Hamiltonian in this way we get

$$H_F = \frac{1}{2} (\omega_m^2 q_m^2 + p_m^2) \quad (31)$$

summed over all modes. Thus we obtain the familiar Hamiltonian of the quantum harmonic oscillator. Now making substitution for q_m & p_m in terms of creation and annihilation operators

$$\widehat{\alpha}_m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\hbar\omega_m}} (\omega_m \widehat{q}_m + i \widehat{p}_m) \quad \widehat{\alpha}_m^* = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\hbar\omega_m}} (\omega_m \widehat{q}_m - i \widehat{p}_m) \quad (32)$$

We can now write the Hamiltonian as

$$H_F = \hbar\omega_m \left(\widehat{\alpha}_m^* \widehat{\alpha}_m + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (33)$$

Now we from basic quantum mechanics know for nth number state of an oscillator the creation and annihilation operators follow the following relations:

$$\widehat{\alpha}_j |i_j\rangle = \sqrt{i_j} |i_j - 1\rangle \quad \widehat{\alpha}_j^* |i_j\rangle = \sqrt{i_j + 1} |i_j + 1\rangle \quad (34)$$

Now we can omit the ground state energy term $\frac{\hbar\omega_m}{2}$ in the field Hamiltonian because the Hamiltonian only depends on the difference of the energies of the states, so this allows us to set the ground state energy to zero with no effect on the eigenstates and eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian. Doing this we get our final field Hamiltonian as

$$\widehat{H}_F = \sum_m \hbar\omega_m \widehat{\alpha}_m^* \widehat{\alpha}_m \quad (35)$$

Hamiltonian of the Dipole Interaction:

Now we formulate the Hamiltonian of the dipole interaction. The interaction is as defined beforehand is the change of the orientation of the electron cloud in the direction of the applied electric field forming a dipole. The total energy of the dipole is thus the product of the force applied and distance the wave function is displaced and which we will be precisely our Hamiltonian. So Hamiltonian of interaction can be written as:

$$H_I = -e\mathbf{E}r = -\mathbf{d}\mathbf{E} \text{ where } \mathbf{d} = e\mathbf{r} \text{ is the dipole term or dipole operator in our case}$$

As stated earlier we are dealing with very long wavelength EM field so the dipole excitation caused by the applied can be thought as a perturbation to the atomic Hamiltonian. Now let us look into the way how the interaction Hamiltonian affects the wave function. By which we mean how the population of a particular state changes with time due to electrons being excited from ground to excited state due to the applied electric field. Let us consider a two level system with states ground state $|\mathbf{a}\rangle$ & excited state $|\mathbf{b}\rangle$ with population number \mathbf{a}^* & \mathbf{b}^* in superposition.

$$|\psi\rangle = \mathbf{a}^*|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^*|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}$$

The wave function evolves according to the Schrodinger equation as:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial |\psi\rangle}{\partial t} = (H_A + H_I)|\psi\rangle \quad (36)$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}}}{\partial t} = H_A |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} \quad \& \quad i\hbar \frac{\partial |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}}{\partial t} = H_A |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} \quad (37)$$

From the above equations we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\mathbf{a}^*|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^*|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}) &= (H_A + H_I)(\mathbf{a}^*|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^*|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}) \\ i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^*}{\partial t} |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{a}^* i\hbar \frac{\partial |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}}}{\partial t} &+ i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^* i\hbar \frac{\partial |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}}{\partial t} \\ &= \mathbf{a}^* H_A |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^* H_A |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} + H_I (\mathbf{a}^*|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^*|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}) \end{aligned}$$

By equation 36 of course this would reduce to

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^*}{\partial t} |\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} |\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} = H_I (\mathbf{a}^*|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^*|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}})$$

Taking inner product of this equation with respect to $|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}$ we obtain:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^*}{\partial t} \langle \mathbf{b}|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} \langle \mathbf{b}|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} = \mathbf{a}^* \langle \mathbf{b}|H_I|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} e^{-i\frac{E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^* \langle \mathbf{b}|H_I|\mathbf{b}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}} e^{-i\frac{E_b t}{\hbar}}$$

By the orthogonality condition, $\langle \mathbf{b}|\mathbf{a}\rangle = 0$, $\langle \mathbf{b}|\mathbf{b}\rangle = 1$ so the equation reduces to

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} = \mathbf{a}^* \langle \mathbf{b}|H_I|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b - E_a t}{\hbar}} + \mathbf{b}^* \langle \mathbf{b}|H_I|\mathbf{b}\rangle$$

Now adhering to our basic assumption of the dipole that the strength of the electromagnetic field is less we also make assumption that the atom is initially in its ground state so all the population of electron is in the ground state and none of it is in the excited state, consequently $\mathbf{a}^* = 1$ & $\mathbf{b}^* = 0$. So our final equation of motion will be as follows:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} = \langle \mathbf{b}|H_I|\mathbf{a}\rangle e^{i\frac{E_b - E_a t}{\hbar}}$$

By equation (3) we can also write this as

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^*}{\partial t} = \hat{\delta}_{ba} e^{i\frac{E_b - E_a t}{\hbar}} \quad (39)$$

So the density operators for the Interaction Hamiltonian are always the off diagonal terms or coherent terms (i.e. $\hat{\sigma}_{ij}$ $i \neq j$), all the diagonal terms being zero. We know that the operator can be written as

$$\hat{d} = |\mathbf{b}\rangle\langle\mathbf{b}|\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{a}\rangle\langle\mathbf{a}| = \langle\mathbf{b}|\mathbf{d}\mathbf{a}\rangle|\mathbf{b}\rangle\langle\mathbf{a}| = \mathbf{d}_{ba}\hat{\sigma}_{ba} \text{ where } \mathbf{d}_{ba} = \langle\mathbf{b}|\mathbf{d}\mathbf{a}\rangle, \hat{\sigma}_{ba} = |\mathbf{b}\rangle\langle\mathbf{a}| \quad (40)$$

So the Hamiltonian of the interaction can be written as $\hat{H}_I = -E\hat{d}_{ba}\hat{\sigma}_{ba}$ $b \neq a$ (41)

Hamiltonian of a three-level lambda system

Three level lambda atom is composed of two hyperfine components of ground state $|\mathbf{b}\rangle$, & $|\mathbf{c}\rangle$ and an excited state $|\mathbf{a}\rangle$. Two laser fields are applied; one coupling from state $|\mathbf{c}\rangle$ to $|\mathbf{a}\rangle$ called coupling laser, & another field coupling from $|\mathbf{b}\rangle$ to $|\mathbf{a}\rangle$ called probe laser. Also $|\mathbf{b}\rangle$ to $|\mathbf{c}\rangle$ transition is dipole forbidden or no population is allowed to make transition between these states as per the spectral theorem. Our assumption is that the probe laser is much weaker than coupling laser. And that by the application of laser the coherent states of the atom do not oscillate rapidly. The dipole interaction will thus be carried out by the electric fields of the probe and coupling lasers. So the Hamiltonian of the system can be written as

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_A + \hat{H}_F + \hat{H}_I$$

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{\mu,\nu=1}^3 \hbar\omega_{\mu}\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu} - \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} (E_p + E_{co})\hat{d}_{\mu\nu}\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} + \sum_m \hbar\omega_m\hat{a}_m^*\hat{a}_m \quad (42)$$

Where E_p & E_c are electric fields of the probe and coupling fields respectively. By matrix mechanics we can represent the Hamiltonian by the matrix $[\langle\mu|\hat{H}|\nu\rangle]$, in terms of the coefficient of the density operator $\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}$. Before we proceed further we must note the basic properties of this density operator or density matrix.

Density matrix is given by the matrix : $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_{11} & \hat{\sigma}_{12} & \hat{\sigma}_{13} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{21} & \hat{\sigma}_{22} & \hat{\sigma}_{23} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{31} & \hat{\sigma}_{32} & \hat{\sigma}_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ where the diagonal terms $\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu}$ represent

the probability density of electron in the μ th state and the off-diagonal terms $\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}$ represents the probability of coherence between two states(likeliness of transition of population of electrons from one state to another so as to get a mixed state). The simple representation makes calculation much easier for us, especially when we need to calculate the probability densities.

Representing the Hamiltonian in (42) terms of the coefficients of the density matrix elements we get

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & -E\hat{d}_{bc} & -E\hat{d}_{ba} \\ -E\hat{d}_{cb} & \hbar\omega_c & -E\hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E\hat{d}_{ab} & -E\hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

But since transition from $|\mathbf{1}\rangle$ to $|\mathbf{2}\rangle$ is dipole forbidden the dipole operators for the required terms must vanish so the Hamiltonian will be

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & 0 & -E\hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c & -E\hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E\hat{d}_{ab} & -E\hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

Or more precisely by substituting $E = E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{co} t)} + \text{cc}$ we get the Hamiltonian as:

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & 0 & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ab} & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

But adhering to our assumption that the atom's coherent states should not rapidly oscillate, our Hamiltonian must not contain rapidly oscillating terms to ensure it we must make a unitary transformation (a transformation which transforms an operator but the eigenstates remain the same) $\hat{U}^* \hat{H} \hat{U}$ where

$$\hat{U} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\omega_b t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-i\omega_c t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{-i\omega_a t} \end{pmatrix}$$

So making the transformation we do what is called Rotating Wave Approximation

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}' &= \hat{U}^* \hat{H} \hat{U} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\omega_b t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\omega_c t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\omega_a t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & 0 & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ab} & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix} \\ &\quad \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\omega_b t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-i\omega_c t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{-i\omega_a t} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\omega_b t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\omega_c t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\omega_a t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b e^{-i\omega_b t} & 0 & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t - \omega_a t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c e^{-i\omega_c t} & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t - \omega_a t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t - \omega_a t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ab} & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r - \omega_p t - \omega_a t)} + E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r - \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a e^{-i\omega_a t} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Now we can take an approximation by saying that only those terms in the above matrix remain which are near resonance or in other words the probe and the control laser beams must not make the population oscillate rapidly except near resonance. So the terms having frequency $\omega_3 - \omega_2 - \omega_c$ or $\omega_3 - \omega_1 - \omega_p$ are near resonant terms and non-rapidly oscillating terms while the terms having frequency $\omega_3 - \omega_2 + \omega_c$ or $\omega_3 - \omega_1 + \omega_p$ are rapidly oscillatory. So we have to omit those terms. Omitting those terms from the above matrix we get

$$\hat{H}' = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & 0 & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t - \omega_a t + \omega_b t)} \hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c & E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r + \omega_{c0} t + \omega_c t - \omega_a t)} \hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t - \omega_a t + \omega_b t)} \hat{d}_{ab} & E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r + \omega_{c0} t - \omega_a t + \omega_c t)} \hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

Transforming the Hamiltonian matrix back to the vector space of $|\mu\rangle$ from $\hat{U}|\mu\rangle$ by the inverse unitary transformation $\hat{U}^* \hat{U} \hat{H} \hat{U} \hat{U}^*$ we get the matrix

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_b & 0 & -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t)} \hat{d}_{ba} \\ 0 & \hbar\omega_c & E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r + \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ca} \\ -E_{p0}e^{i(k_p r + \omega_p t)} \hat{d}_{ab} & E_{c0}e^{i(k_c r + \omega_{c0} t)} \hat{d}_{ac} & \hbar\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

We can also make another unitary transformation to get rid of the time dependent terms and any phase terms if present, the unitary transformation being

$$\hat{U} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\omega_p t - i\phi_p t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-i\omega_{c0} t - i\phi_c t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Applying this transformation, we get the matrix

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 2(\omega_b + \omega_p) & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 2(\omega_c + \omega_{co}) & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2\omega_a \end{pmatrix}$$

Where $\Omega_p = \frac{E_{p0}\hat{d}_{ba}}{\hbar}$, $\Omega_c = \frac{E_{c0}\hat{d}_{ca}}{\hbar}$ are called Rabi frequencies.

We can simplify further by making use of the fact that by changing the energy of the system by some constant leave the eigenstate unchanged, as the energy of the eigenstates depend on the difference of the energies of the system. So we can transform the Hamiltonian by $\hat{H} \rightarrow \hat{H} - I \frac{\hbar}{2} 2(\omega_b + \omega_p)$ so we finally get the Hamiltonian matrix

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 2(\omega_c + \omega_{co} - \omega_b - \omega_p) & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2(\omega_a - \omega_b - \omega_p) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 2(\omega_{co} - (\omega_a - \omega_c) - \omega_p + (\omega_a - \omega_b)) & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2(\omega_a - \omega_b - \omega_p) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 2(\Delta_p - \Delta_c) & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2\Delta_p \end{pmatrix}$$

where $\Delta_p = (\omega_a - \omega_b) - \omega_p$ and $\Delta_c = (\omega_a - \omega_c) - \omega_c$ are called detuning terms. For simplicity we assume $\Delta_p \cong \Delta_c$, by doing this we get the final EIT Hamiltonian as

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2\Delta_p \end{pmatrix}$$

Eigenstates and Energy eigenvalues of the EIT Hamiltonian:

The three energy eigenvalues are $\epsilon_0 = 0$, $\epsilon_+ = \frac{\hbar}{2} \left(\Delta_p + \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2} \right)$,

$\epsilon_- = \frac{\hbar}{2} \left(\Delta_p - \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2} \right)$, and the corresponding eigenvectors are:

$$|D\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle - \left(\frac{\Omega_c}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle,$$

$$|B_+\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p}{\Delta_p + \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle + \left(\frac{\Omega_c}{\Delta_p + \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle - |a\rangle$$

$$|B_-\rangle = - \left(\frac{\Omega_p}{\Delta_p - \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle - \left(\frac{\Omega_c}{\Delta_p - \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle + |a\rangle$$

Defining angles θ & ϕ such that $\tan\theta = \frac{\Omega_p}{\Omega_c}$ & $\tan\phi = \frac{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}}{\Delta_p + \sqrt{\Delta_p^2 + \Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}}$ we can write the states as

$$|D\rangle = \cos\theta |b\rangle - \sin\theta |c\rangle \quad |B_+\rangle = \sin\theta\cos\phi |b\rangle + \cos\theta\cos\phi |c\rangle + \cos\phi |a\rangle$$

$$|B_-\rangle = \sin\theta\cos\phi |b\rangle + \cos\theta\cos\phi |c\rangle - \sin\phi |a\rangle$$

Now if we apply take the inner product of the $|D\rangle$ with the Hamiltonian \hat{H} & the excited state $|a\rangle$

$$\text{gives } \langle D|\hat{H}|c\rangle = (\cos\theta \langle b| - \sin\theta \langle c|) \frac{\hbar}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_p \\ \mathbf{0} & 0 & -\Omega_c \\ -\Omega_p & -\Omega_c & 2\Delta_p \end{pmatrix} |c\rangle = 0$$

Therefore the atom in the state $|D\rangle$ never make transition to excited state, that is why it is called a dark state.

Dark state, Bright state and Excited states:

We can also represent the atomic states by the superposition of the eigenstates as:

$$|D\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle - \left(\frac{\Omega_c}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle, \quad |B\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p^*}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle + \left(\frac{\Omega_c^*}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle$$

$|E\rangle = |a\rangle$, known respectively as the dark, bright & the excited state.

Langevin's equations of motion:

Now to exactly know the details of the electron populations' motion we need to solve the equations in the variables of the density matrix elements. Therefore, first we recall from the form of the Hamiltonian for the lambda system derived earlier in terms of density matrix elements, which is

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^3 \hbar\omega_{\mu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu} - \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} (\mathbf{E}_p + \mathbf{E}_{co}) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} + \sum_m \hbar\omega_m \hat{\mathbf{a}}_m^* \hat{\mathbf{a}}_m$$

Also we know from basic postulates of quantum mechanics that to know the time rate change of any operator present in the Hamiltonian we need to take its commutator with the Hamiltonian, so time rate change of the density matrix elements can be obtained using

$$\dot{\hat{\sigma}}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{i\hbar} [\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}, \hat{H}]$$

For density matrix elements $|\mu\rangle\langle\nu|$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{\sigma}}_{\mu\nu} &= \frac{1}{i\hbar} [\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}, \hat{H}] = \frac{1}{i\hbar} (\hbar\omega_{cb} (\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{cc} - \hat{\sigma}_{cc} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}) + \hbar\omega_{ab} (\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{aa} - \hat{\sigma}_{aa} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}) - \\ &(\mathbf{E}_p + \mathbf{E}_{co}) ((\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{ba} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{ba} - \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{ba} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}) + (\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{ca} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{ca} - \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{ca} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu})) \end{aligned}$$

By applying rotating frame approximation, we get

$$\dot{\sigma}_{aa} = \frac{-i}{\hbar} (\mathbf{E}_p^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ba} \sigma_{ba} + \mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca} \sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.})$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{bb} = \frac{i}{\hbar} (\mathbf{E}_p^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ba} \sigma_{ba} - \text{h.a.})$$

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\sigma}_{cc} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}\sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.}) \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ba} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}(\sigma_{bb} - \sigma_{aa}) + \mathbf{E}_c^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ac}\sigma_{bc}) - i\delta_p \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ca} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ac}(\sigma_{cc} - \sigma_{aa}) + \mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}\sigma_{cb}) - i\delta_c \\ \dot{\sigma}_{bc} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}\sigma_{ba} - \mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}\sigma_{ac}) - i\Delta\end{aligned}$$

But actual atomic system does not show such simple behavior. In addition to the transition of the population of the electrons from the ground and meta stable state to the excited state, the excited state suffers spontaneous emission of population to lower energy states due to electron-electron interactions. That is why we need to add the spontaneous emission term to the equations above. Doing which the equations above will be

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\sigma}_{aa} &= \frac{-i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_p^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ba}\sigma_{ba} + \mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}\sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.}) - \gamma\sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{bb} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_p^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ba}\sigma_{ba} - \text{h.a.}) + \gamma_b\sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{cc} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}\sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.}) + \gamma_c\sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ba} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}(\sigma_{bb} - \sigma_{aa}) + \mathbf{E}_c^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ac}\sigma_{bc}) - \Gamma_{ba}\sigma_{ba} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ca} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ac}(\sigma_{cc} - \sigma_{aa}) + \mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}\sigma_{cb}) - \Gamma_{ca}\sigma_{ca} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{bc} &= \frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathbf{E}_c^c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}\sigma_{ba} - \mathbf{E}_p^a \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ab}\sigma_{ac}) - \Gamma_{bc}\sigma_{bc}\end{aligned}$$

where γ is the spontaneous emission rate from the excited state, γ_b & γ_c are the rate of addition of the population of electrons to the two hyperfine components of ground state due to spontaneous emission from the excited state to the levels. $\Gamma_{ba} = \gamma_{ba} - i\Delta_p$, $\Gamma_{ca} = \gamma_{ca} - i\Delta_c$, $\Gamma_{bc} = \gamma_{bc} - i\Delta$ where γ_{ba} , γ_{ca} & γ_{bc} are spontaneous emission rate of population from the respective coherent states. Taking the expectation values of all the density matrix operators above we get

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\rho}_{aa} &= i(\Omega_p\rho_{ba} + \Omega_c\rho_{ca} - \text{c.c.}) - \gamma\rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{bb} &= -i(\Omega_p\rho_{ba} - \text{c.c.}) + \gamma_b\rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{cc} &= -i(\Omega_c\rho_{ca} - \text{c.c.}) + \gamma_c\rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{ab} &= i\Omega_p(\rho_{bb} - \rho_{aa}) + i\Omega_c\rho_{cb} - \Gamma_{ba}\rho_{ab} \\ \dot{\rho}_{ac} &= i\Omega_c(\rho_{cc} - \rho_{aa}) + i\Omega_p\rho_{bc} - \Gamma_{ca}\rho_{ac} \\ \dot{\rho}_{cb} &= i(\Omega_c^*\rho_{ab} - \Omega_p\rho_{ca}) - \Gamma_{bc}\rho_{cb}\end{aligned}$$

Now to devise a more convenient form of formulation we can represent the Hamiltonian of the lambda system

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{\mu,\nu=1}^3 \hbar\omega_{\mu}\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu} - \sum_{\mu\neq\nu} (\mathbf{E}_p + \mathbf{E}_{co})\hat{d}_{\mu\nu}\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu} + \sum_m \hbar\omega_m\hat{a}_m^*\hat{a}_m$$

In the rotating frame, by changing the basis state $|\mu\rangle$ to the dark, bright and excited basis states, which we previously defined as

$$|D\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle - \left(\frac{\Omega_c}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle, \quad |B\rangle = \left(\frac{\Omega_p^*}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |b\rangle + \left(\frac{\Omega_c^*}{\sqrt{\Omega_p^2 + \Omega_c^2}} \right) |c\rangle$$

$$|E\rangle = |a\rangle$$

We will get the new Hamiltonian as:

$$\hat{H}' = -\hbar\delta_p\sigma_{EE} - \hbar\Omega(\sigma_{EB} + \sigma_{BE})$$

For making calculations more easily we make assumption $\gamma_b = \gamma_c$ such that $\gamma_{bc} = 0$ thus we can rewrite the density matrix equation previously derived in the rest frame, in the rotating frame as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\rho}_{EE} &= -i\Omega(\rho_{EB} - \text{c.c.}) - \gamma\rho_{EE} \\ \dot{\rho}_{BB} &= i\Omega(\rho_{EB} - \text{c.c.}) + \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{EE} \\ \dot{\rho}_{DD} &= \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{EE} \\ \dot{\rho}_{EB} &= i\delta_p\rho_{EB} + i\Omega(\rho_{BB} - \rho_{EE}) - \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{EB} \\ \dot{\rho}_{ED} &= i\delta_p\rho_{ED} + i\Omega\rho_{BD} - \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{ED} \\ \dot{\rho}_{BD} &= i\Omega\rho_{ED} \end{aligned}$$

We now need to calculate the steady state solutions $\rho_{\mu\nu}^{st}$ of the probability densities by setting $\dot{\rho}_{\mu\nu} = 0$, we immediately find $\rho_{EE}^{st} = 0$, also $\rho_{EB}^{st} = \rho_{BE}^{st}$ also we find

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= i\delta_p\rho_{EB} + i\Omega\rho_{BB} - \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{EB} \\ 0 &= -i\delta_p\rho_{EB} - i\Omega\rho_{BB} - \frac{\gamma}{2}\rho_{EB}. \end{aligned}$$

Adding the above two equations we get $\rho_{BE}^{st} = 0$ consequently also $\rho_{BB}^{st} = 0$. The atom will likely not be in the excited state or bright state at equilibrium. By normalization condition

$$\rho_{DD} + \rho_{BB} + \rho_{EE} = 1$$

We find therefore $\rho_{DD}^{st} = 1$ which means the lambda atom succumbs to dark state when two photon detuning $\Delta = 0$ along with the dephasing rate $\gamma_{bc} = 0$.

Susceptibility of the Lambda System:

By classical electrodynamics of matter, we know the polarization is defined as the product of the density of the matter and the dipole moments present in it.

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \varrho \langle \mathbf{d} \rangle$$

Here ϱ is the density of the medium, $\langle \mathbf{d} \rangle$ is the expectation value of the dipole operator. We assume the density matrix elements are slowly varying and they do not undergo very rapid change in their value at equilibrium. Under slowly varying condition the density matrix elements can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu}(t) &= \sigma_{\mu\mu}(t) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{ba}(t) &= \sigma_{ba}(t)e^{-i\omega_p t} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{ca}(t) &= \sigma_{ca}(t)e^{-i\omega_c t} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{bc}(t) &= \sigma_{bc}(t)e^{-i(\omega_p - \omega_c)t}\end{aligned}$$

The expectation value of the dipole moment operator can be written as

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \varrho (\mathbf{d}_{ba}\rho_{ab}e^{-i\omega_p t} + \mathbf{d}_{ca}\rho_{ac}e^{-i\omega_c t})$$

We know electrical susceptibility of the medium is given as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}(\omega) = \varepsilon_0 \chi_e(\omega) \tilde{\mathbf{E}}(\omega)$$

Substituting for the $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ in the above equation we get the relation

$$\varrho \mathbf{d}_{ba} \rho_{ab}^{st} = \varepsilon_0 \chi_e(\omega_p) \mathbf{E}_{p,0} e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}}$$

To know the values of the static density matrix element

We must solve the density matrix equations by perturbation theory. We assume Rabi frequency of the control laser is much greater than that of the probe laser $\Omega_p \ll \Omega_c$. Breaking down the density matrix elements in the power series where we define $\epsilon = \frac{\Omega_p}{\Omega_c}$

$$\rho_{\mu\nu} = \rho_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} + \rho_{\mu\nu}^{(1)}\epsilon + \rho_{\mu\nu}^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + \dots$$

Inserting them in the Langevin's equations previously derived for lambda system which are

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\rho}_{aa} &= i(\Omega_p \rho_{ba} + \Omega_c \rho_{ca} - \text{c.c.}) - \gamma \rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{bb} &= -i(\Omega_p \rho_{ba} - \text{c.c.}) + \gamma_b \rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{cc} &= -i(\Omega_c \rho_{ca} - \text{c.c.}) + \gamma_c \rho_{aa} \\ \dot{\rho}_{ab} &= i\Omega_p(\rho_{bb} - \rho_{aa}) + i\Omega_c \rho_{cb} - \Gamma_{ba} \rho_{ab} \\ \dot{\rho}_{ac} &= i\Omega_c(\rho_{cc} - \rho_{aa}) + i\Omega_p \rho_{bc} - \Gamma_{ca} \rho_{ac} \\ \dot{\rho}_{cb} &= i(\Omega_c^* \rho_{ab} - \Omega_p \rho_{ca}) - \Gamma_{bc} \rho_{cb}\end{aligned}$$

and setting $\rho_{\mu\nu}^i = 0$, and also considering only the first order term in ϵ , under assumption that initially only ground state is populated ($\rho_{cc}^{st} = 0, \rho_{aa}^{st} = 0$ & $\rho_{bb}^{st} = 1$, we get the two equations as follows

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= i\Omega_p + i\Omega_c \rho_{cb}^{st} - \Gamma_{ba} \rho_{ab}^{st} \\ 0 &= i\Omega_c^* \rho_{ab}^{st} - \Gamma_{bc} \rho_{cb}^{st}. \end{aligned}$$

The solution for the ρ_{ab}^{st} can be given as

$$\rho_{ab}^{st} = i\Omega_p \frac{\Gamma_{bc}}{\Gamma_{ba}\Gamma_{bc} + |\Omega_c|^2}$$

Substituting for ρ_{ab}^{st} in the relation of the susceptibility and solving for the susceptibility we get

$$\chi_e(\omega_p) = \frac{\varrho |\mathbf{d}_{ab}|^2}{\hbar \varepsilon_0} \frac{i\Gamma_{bc}}{\Gamma_{ba}\Gamma_{bc} + |\Omega_c|^2}$$

The real and imaginary part of the susceptibility are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_e' &= \frac{\varrho |\mathbf{d}_{ab}|^2}{\hbar \varepsilon_0} \frac{\Delta |\Omega_c|^2 - \delta_p (\Delta^2 + \gamma_{bc}^2)}{(|\Omega_c|^2 + \gamma_{ba}\gamma_{bc} - \delta_p \Delta)^2 + (\delta_p \gamma_{bc} + \gamma_{ba} \Delta)^2} \\ \chi_e'' &= \frac{\varrho |\mathbf{d}_{ab}|^2}{\hbar \varepsilon_0} \frac{\gamma_{ba} \Delta^2 + \gamma_{bc} (|\Omega_c|^2 + \gamma_{ba}\gamma_{bc})}{(|\Omega_c|^2 + \gamma_{ba}\gamma_{bc} - \delta_p \Delta)^2 + (\delta_p \gamma_{bc} + \gamma_{ba} \Delta)^2} \end{aligned}$$

Fig : Plot of the real (dashed) and the imaginary susceptibility as a function of probe laser tuning

Studying the graph, we easily find the drop in the susceptibility when detuning is zero; this is when the probe laser is not absorbed by the atom, opening a transparency window, which is actual finding in the electromagnetically induced transparency experiments.

The group velocity of the probe pulse is given by

$$v_g(\omega_p) = \frac{c}{1 + \omega_p \frac{\rho |\mathbf{d}_{ab}|^2}{2\hbar \epsilon_0 |\Omega_c|^2}}$$

Pulse propagation through EIT medium:

Now as we have known the dielectric property of the medium, we are now ready to device a formulation to see how a probe laser pulse actually propagates through this medium. To see this, we first of all must rewrite the lambda atom Hamiltonian for N such lambda atoms. The Hamiltonian will be

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^3 \hbar \omega_{\mu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu}^j - \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} (\mathbf{E}_p(\mathbf{r}_j) + \mathbf{E}_{co}(\mathbf{r}_j)) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}^j + \sum_m \hbar \omega_m \hat{\mathbf{a}}_m^* \hat{\mathbf{a}}_m \right)$$

We can again assume the density matrix elements are slowly varying so the following holds true

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu}^j(t) &= \sigma_{\mu\mu}^j(t) \\ \hat{\sigma}_{ba}^j(t) &= \sigma_{ba}^j(t) e^{i(\mathbf{k}_p \cdot \mathbf{r}_j - \omega_p t)} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{ca}^j(t) &= \sigma_{ca}^j(t) e^{i(\mathbf{k}_c \cdot \mathbf{r}_j - \omega_c t)} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{bc}^j(t) &= \sigma_{bc}^j(t) e^{i((\mathbf{k}_p - \mathbf{k}_c) \cdot \mathbf{r}_j - (\omega_p - \omega_c)t)} \end{aligned}$$

The Heisenberg Langevin's equation will be now

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\sigma}_{aa} &= -ig_p (E_p^\dagger \sigma_{ba} - \text{h.a.}) - ig_c (E_c^\dagger \sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.}) - \gamma \sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{bb} &= ig_p (E_p^\dagger \sigma_{ba} - \text{h.a.}) + \gamma_b \sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{cc} &= ig_c (E_c^\dagger \sigma_{ca} - \text{h.a.}) + \gamma_c \sigma_{aa} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ba} &= ig_p E_p (\sigma_{bb} - \sigma_{aa}) + ig_c E_c \sigma_{bc} - \Gamma_{ba} \sigma_{ba} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{ca} &= ig_c E_c (\sigma_{cc} - \sigma_{aa}) + ig_p E_p \sigma_{bc}^\dagger - \Gamma_{ca} \sigma_{ca} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{bc} &= i (g_c E_c^\dagger \sigma_{ba} - g_p E_p \sigma_{ca}^\dagger) - \Gamma_{bc} \sigma_{bc} \end{aligned}$$

We substituted

$$g_p = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_p}{2\hbar \epsilon_0 V}} \mathbf{e}_p \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ba} \quad g_c = \sqrt{\frac{\omega_c}{2\hbar \epsilon_0 V}} \mathbf{e}_c \cdot \mathbf{d}_{ca}$$

By classical electrodynamics we know the wave equations in a polarized medium is given by

$$\nabla^2 \hat{\mathbf{E}} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\mathbf{E}}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{\mathbf{P}}}{\partial t^2}$$

We also have the derived the expression of the dipole operator as

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}_j = \mathbf{d}_{ba} \sigma_{ba}^j(t) e^{i(\mathbf{k}_p \cdot \mathbf{r}_j - \omega_p t)} + \mathbf{d}_{ca} \sigma_{ca}^j(t) e^{i(\mathbf{k}_c \cdot \mathbf{r}_j - \omega_c t)}$$

So the Polarization can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{N_{\mathbf{r}}}{V} \left(\mathbf{d}_{ba} \sigma_{ba} e^{i(\mathbf{k}_p \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega_p t)} + \mathbf{d}_{ca} \sigma_{ca} e^{i(\mathbf{k}_c \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega_c t)} + \text{h.a.} \right)$$

Substituting the polarization in the wave equation above we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar \omega_p}{2 \epsilon_0 V}} \mathbf{e}_p \left(\frac{\partial^2 E_p}{\partial z^2} + 2ik_p \frac{\partial E_p}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_p}{\partial t^2} + \frac{2i\omega_p}{c^2} \frac{\partial E_p}{\partial t} \right) \\ = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2} \frac{N_{\mathbf{r}}}{V} \mathbf{d}_{ba} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_{ba}}{\partial t^2} - 2i\omega_p \frac{\partial \sigma_{ba}}{\partial t} - \omega_p^2 \sigma_{ba} \right) \end{aligned}$$

But since all the density matrix operators and the electric probe field has to be slowly we must make a variable change which is

$$t' = \frac{t}{T_p} \quad z' = \frac{z}{L_p}$$

Here the T_p & L_p are the characteristic time and length scale of the process. For the process to be slowly varying we must approximate that

$$T_{p,c} \gg \omega_{p,c}^{-1} \quad L_{p,c} \gg k_{p,c}^{-1}$$

Substituting for t and z in the above polarization wave equation and abiding by the above condition the second order differential will be so small that we can omit them, so the propagation wave equation of the probe field can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) E_p(z, t) &= ig_p N_{\mathbf{r}}(z) \sigma_{ba}(z, t) \\ \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) E_c(z, t) &= ig_c N_{\mathbf{r}}(z) \sigma_{ca}(z, t) \end{aligned}$$

Now analytically solving the above two propagation equations and the coupled Heisenberg Langevin's equation is impossible. So the easiest approach is to solve them by the perturbation method. We make another approximation here that the probe pulse is much weaker than the control pulse. Such the ratio ϵ of the amplitudes of the probe and control pulse approaches zero.

$$\epsilon = \frac{E_{p,max}}{E_{c,max}},$$

For perturbation solution we will have to expand the matrix elements and probe field and control field in the powers of ϵ .

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{\mu\nu} &= \sigma_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} + \epsilon\sigma_{\mu\nu}^{(1)} + \epsilon^2\sigma_{\mu\nu}^{(2)} + \dots \\ E_p &= E_p^{(0)} + \epsilon E_p^{(1)} + \epsilon^2 E_p^{(2)} + \dots \\ E_c &= E_c^{(0)} + \epsilon E_c^{(1)} + \epsilon^2 E_c^{(2)} + \dots\end{aligned}$$

We choose the initial condition that only the ground state is populated and all the coherent terms and excited state terms in the density matrix is zero so the following holds

$$\sigma_{bb}^{(0)} \rightarrow \hat{1} \quad \sigma_{\mu\nu}^{(0)} \rightarrow \hat{0} \quad \text{for } \mu\nu \neq bb$$

Taking the terms up to first order in ϵ , we get from the Langevin's equation

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ba} &= \frac{1}{ig_c E_c^*} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{bc} \right] \sigma_{bc}, \\ \sigma_{bc} &= -\frac{g_p E_p}{g_c E_c} + \frac{1}{ig_c E_c} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{ba} \right] \sigma_{ba}\end{aligned}$$

Inserting the value of σ_{ba} in the equation of σ_{bc} we obtain

$$\sigma_{bc} = -\frac{g_p E_p}{g_c E_c} + \frac{1}{ig_c E_c} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{ba} \right] \left(\frac{1}{ig_c E_c^*} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{bc} \right] \sigma_{bc} \right)$$

The number state representation of the N lambda atom Hamiltonian:

Now for information storage by photon states in an EIT system we need to represent the Hamiltonian in terms of number states rather than in density states, for obvious reason that the photon states will store the information for us in here. So first of all we rewrite the N lambda atom Hamiltonian for the system as previously derived

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\sum_{\mu,\nu=1}^3 \hbar\omega_{\mu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\mu}^j - \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} (E_p(\mathbf{r}_j) + E_c(\mathbf{r}_j)) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\mu\nu} \hat{\sigma}_{\mu\nu}^j + \hbar\omega_p \hat{\mathbf{d}}_p^* \hat{\mathbf{d}}_p + \hbar\omega_c \hat{\mathbf{d}}_c^* \hat{\mathbf{d}}_c \right)$$

Here actually we breakup creation and annihilation operators $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_m^* \hat{\mathbf{a}}_m$ into the creation and annihilation operators of the probe and the control beam suited to our purpose.

The fields operators are given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}^a + \hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}^c$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}^a(\mathbf{r}, t) = i\sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega_{p,c}}{2\epsilon_0}} \mathbf{u}_{p,c}(\mathbf{r}) \hat{d}_{p,c}(t) \quad \hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}^c = \left(\hat{\mathbf{E}}_{p,c}^a \right)^\dagger$$

Also we need to again define density matrix elements as spatially slowly varying

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\sigma}_{ba}^j &= \sigma_{ba}^j e^{ik_p z} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{ca}^j &= \sigma_{ca}^j e^{ik_c z}\end{aligned}$$

Applying the rotating wave approximation, we previously invoked to derive the Hamiltonian of one lambda atom as

$$\hat{U} = e^{-i(\omega_p \hat{d}_p^\dagger \hat{d}_p + \omega_c \hat{d}_c^\dagger \hat{d}_c + (\omega_p - \omega_c) \hat{\sigma}_{cc} + \omega_p \hat{\sigma}_{aa})t}$$

We get the Hamiltonian for N lambda atoms

$$\hat{H}' = -\hbar \sum_{j=1}^N \left[\Delta \sigma_{cc}^j + \delta_p \sigma_{aa}^j - \left(ig_p \hat{d}_p^\dagger \sigma_{ba}^j + ig_c \hat{d}_c^\dagger \sigma_{ca}^j + \text{h.a.} \right) \right]$$

By principles of quantum mechanics, we know that we can represent ordinary quantum states for distinguishable particles (Fermions or Bosons) in terms of number states which are very easy to handle. Instead of representing the states of a system in usual form as state operators $|i\rangle$, we can also represent the same thing as creation operators operating on the ground state. These states are called fock states. The fock states will follow the usual properties of the creation and annihilation operators which are

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger |n_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle &= \sqrt{n_{\mathbf{k}} + 1} |n_{\mathbf{k}} + 1\rangle \\ b_{\mathbf{k}} |n_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle &= \sqrt{n_{\mathbf{k}}} |n_{\mathbf{k}} - 1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Here $|n_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle$ is the fock state. In this formulation our above Hamiltonian can be rewritten as

$$\hat{H}' = -\hbar \Delta \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{c} - \hbar \delta_p \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \hbar \left(ig_p \hat{d}_p^\dagger \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{a} + ig_c \hat{d}_c^\dagger \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{a} + \text{h.a.} \right)$$

Here $\hat{a}, \hat{b}, \hat{c}$ are the creation/annihilation operators of the states $|a\rangle, |b\rangle, \& |c\rangle$ states respectively, and the basis states is now represented by the

$$|a^i b^j c^k, n_p, n_c\rangle$$

Here i, j, k are the number of atoms occupying the particular state, n_p & n_c are the photon numbers of the probe and control field respectively. When the creation/annihilation operator for a particular state operates on the fock basis states they increase/decrease the occupation numbers.

Generalized dark state and quantum memory:

We now derive the dark states in N lambda atoms. We assume that control laser is powerful enough so that we can consider it as a classical field; so instead of writing it as in terms of creation/annihilation operator we can write it as Rabi frequency.

$$g_c \hat{d}_c^\dagger \rightarrow \Omega_c$$

So we can write our Hamiltonian as

$$\hat{H}' = -\hbar \delta_p \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \hbar \left(ig_p \hat{d}_p^\dagger \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{a} + i\Omega_c \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{a} + \text{h.a.} \right)$$

As previously found that the dark state will be a combination of two hyperfine components of ground state, but it won't contain the excited so the dark state can be represented as

$$|D', n\rangle = \sum_{k=0}^n \alpha_k |b^{(N-k)} c^k, n-k\rangle$$

Where n is the total number of photons in the probe field and k is the number of atoms in $|c\rangle$ state, while N is the total number of atoms present.

Now we need to find the coefficient α_k . We do this by applying the Hamiltonian matrix on the dark state, by doing which we will obviously get zero as earlier case.

$$\hat{H}' |D', n\rangle = 0$$

From this equation we get the recursion relation

$$\alpha_{k+1} = -\frac{g_p}{\Omega_c} \sqrt{\frac{(N-k)(n-k)}{k+1}} \alpha_k$$

Solving which we get

$$\alpha_k = \alpha_0 \left(-\frac{g_p}{\Omega_c}\right)^k \sqrt{\frac{N!n!}{k!(N-k)!(n-k)!}}$$

Making approximation that $N \gg n$, we will get the easier expression

$$\alpha_k = \alpha_0 \left(-\frac{g_p \sqrt{N}}{\Omega_c}\right)^k \sqrt{\frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}}$$

But the coefficients α_k must satisfy the normalizing condition

$$\sum_{k=0}^n |\alpha_k|^2 = 1$$

This leads to the expression

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \alpha_0^2 \left(\frac{g_p^2 N}{\Omega_c^2}\right)^k = 1$$

This is exactly equivalent to the expression of binomial expansion which is

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^n \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^k = (x+y)^n$$

Now they would be same if we take $x = \cos^2 \theta$, & $y = \sin^2 \theta$, we get $\alpha_0 = \cos^n \theta$ & $\frac{g_p \sqrt{N}}{\Omega_c} = \tan \theta$.

Here θ is the mixing angle satisfying

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\Omega_c}{\sqrt{g_p^2 N + \Omega_c^2}} \quad \sin \theta = \frac{g_p \sqrt{N}}{\sqrt{g_p^2 N + \Omega_c^2}}$$

Therefore, the dark states are given by the expression

$$|D', n\rangle = \sum_{k=0}^n \sqrt{\frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}} (-\sin\theta)^k (\cos\theta)^{n-k} |b^{N-k}c^k, n-k\rangle$$

Now if $\Omega_c \gg g_p\sqrt{N}$ then the mixing angle $\theta \rightarrow 0$ so the dark state will be given by

$$|D', n\rangle = |b^N, n\rangle$$

The atoms will be in the ground state. But if the control laser is adiabatically switched off then, $\Omega_c = 0$. So the mixing angle $\theta \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}$. The dark state now will be

$$|D', n\rangle = |b^{N-n}c^n, 0\rangle$$

Due to the process being an adiabatic one from basic principle of quantum mechanics we know that when a process is done adiabatically over a very long time then the system remains in the same eigenstate due to the slow perturbation acting on the system.

So the system will eventually evolve into the instantaneous eigenstate as soon as the control field is adiabatically turned off.

$$\sum_{n,m} \rho_{nm} |n\rangle\langle m| \otimes |b^N\rangle\langle b^N| \rightarrow |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes \sum_{n,m} \rho_{nm} |b^{N-n}c^n\rangle\langle b^{N-m}c^m|$$

The information gets stored in the configuration of the populations in the given instantaneous eigenstate. When the control field is turned on again the process is reversed and the excitation due to the probe is undone and the information is retrieved by the outgoing probe pulse.

Propagation of Dark Polariton Fields

Now in order to show how the pulse inside the material exactly behave, we need to solve the pulse propagation equations we previously derived for the dark state of the atom. The propagation equation of the probe and control fields derived are

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) E_p(z, t) &= ig_p N_{\mathbf{r}}(z) \sigma_{ba}(z, t) \\ \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) E_c(z, t) &= ig_c N_{\mathbf{r}}(z) \sigma_{ca}(z, t) \end{aligned}$$

The equations governing change in the density matrix operators derived earlier are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ba} &= \frac{1}{ig_c E_c^*} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{bc} \right] \sigma_{bc}, \\ \sigma_{bc} &= -\frac{g_p E_p}{g_c E_c} + \frac{1}{ig_c E_c} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{ba} \right] \sigma_{ba} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting for the σ_{ba} in the propagation equation of probe field we get

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) E_p(z, t) = \frac{g_p N_{\mathbf{r}}}{\Omega_c(t)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{bc} \right) \sigma_{bc}$$

Now we define the Polariton field operators. Polariton are actually quasi-particles which originates when the electromagnetic fields couples strongly with a dipole interaction. Polaritons can be represented by linear combination of the probe field and coherent terms of the density matrix elements.

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi &= \cos \theta E_p - \sin \theta \sqrt{N_{\mathbf{r}}} \sigma_{bc} \\ \Phi &= \sin \theta E_p + \cos \theta \sqrt{N_{\mathbf{r}}} \sigma_{bc} \end{aligned}$$

Ψ & Φ are the dark Polariton field and bright Polariton field operators respectively. The quantum memory is stored by dark Polariton probe field.

Representing the probe field E_p & coherent density matrix term $\hat{\sigma}_{bc}$ in terms of Ψ & Φ we get

$$\begin{aligned} E_p &= \sin \theta \Phi + \cos \theta \Psi \\ \sqrt{N_{\mathbf{r}}} \sigma_{bc} &= \cos \theta \Phi - \sin \theta \Psi \end{aligned}$$

Now substituting for the E_p & $\hat{\sigma}_{bc}$ in the propagation equation of probe field and the expression for $\hat{\sigma}_{ba}$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} + c \cos^2 \theta \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} &= -\dot{\theta} \Phi - c \sin \theta \cos \theta \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} - \Gamma_{bc} (\sin^2 \theta \Psi - \sin \theta \cos \theta \Phi) \\ \Phi &= \frac{\sin \theta}{g_p^2 N_{\mathbf{r}}} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{ba} \right] \left(\tan \theta \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma_{bc} \right] \right) (\sin \theta \Psi - \cos \theta \Phi) \end{aligned}$$

To solve the above equation more easily we make an approximation that the two photon detuning is negligible ($\Gamma_{bc} \cong 0$), also because we are about to have a adiabatic process by storing the Polariton inside the atom, we must have a very small timescale for the process we must have what we call a characteristic timescale for the process which define as

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{g_p \sqrt{N_{\mathbf{r}}} T}$$

We can now solve the field equations by perturbation by expanding the fields Ψ & Φ in terms of the ζ . $\Psi = \Psi_0 + \zeta \Psi^{(1)} + \zeta^2 \Psi^{(2)} + \dots$.

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 + \zeta \Phi^{(1)} + \zeta^2 \Phi^{(2)} + \dots$$

Keeping up to the second order approximation we first calculate the bright Polariton field Φ in order to incorporate the fact can there be rapid change in the control laser intensity which perturb the BSP up to second order approximately. By doing which we get

$$\Phi = \frac{\sin \theta}{g_p^2 N_{\mathbf{r}}} \left[\Gamma_{ba} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right] \left(\tan \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\sin \theta \Psi) \right)$$

Also approximate dark state Polariton field to zeroth order we get the equation

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = -c \cos^2 \theta \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z}$$

Substituting this in the expression of Φ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & \frac{\sin \theta}{g_p^2 N_r} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\dot{\theta} \sin \theta) \Psi - \dot{\theta} \sin \theta \cos^2 \theta c \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\sin^2 \theta \cos \theta) c \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} \right. \\ & \left. + \sin^2 \theta \cos^3 \theta c^2 \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial z^2} \right] + \frac{\Gamma_{ba}}{g_p^2 N_r} \left[\dot{\theta} \sin^2 \theta \Psi - \sin^3 \theta \cos \theta c \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Inserting the expression of the BSP Φ in the wave equation of DSP derived earlier which is

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} + c \cos^2 \theta \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} = -\dot{\theta} \Phi - c \sin \theta \cos \theta \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} - \Gamma_{bc} (\sin^2 \theta \Psi - \sin \theta \cos \theta \Phi)$$

We get the following equation

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \cos^2 \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right] \Psi = -A(t) \Psi + B(t) c \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} + C(t) c^2 \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial z^2} - D(t) c^3 \frac{\partial^3 \Psi}{\partial z^3}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} A(t) &= \left(\Gamma_{ba} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \left(\frac{\dot{\theta}^2 \sin^2 \theta}{g_p^2 N_r} \right), \\ B(t) &= \frac{\sin \theta}{g_p^2 N_r} \left(2\dot{\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\sin^2 \theta \cos \theta) - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \sin^3 \theta \right) \\ C(t) &= \left(\Gamma_{ba} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \frac{\sin^4 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{g_p^2 N_r}, \\ D(t) &= \frac{\sin^4 \theta \cos^4 \theta}{g_p^2 N_r}. \end{aligned}$$

The $A(t)$ is the describes homogenous losses due to non-adiabatic transitions to the excited state $|a\rangle$, caused by the rapid switching of the coupling laser intensity, followed by spontaneous emission. $B(t)$ gives a correction to the group velocity of the DSP field. $C(t)$ leads to broadening of the pulse shape due to absorption of high spatial frequency components of the DSP field. Finally, $D(t)$ is responsible for a deformation of the pulse shape.

Now the solution of the wave equation of the DSP field can be found by the fourier transform method which is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Psi}(q, t) = & \tilde{\Psi}(q, 0) \exp \left(-iqc \int_0^t (\cos^2 \theta(t') - B(t')) dt' \right) \times \\ & \exp \left(- \int_0^t A(t') dt' \right) \exp \left(-q^2 c^2 \int_0^t C(t') dt' \right) \exp \left(iq^3 c^3 \int_0^t D(t') dt' \right) \end{aligned}$$

We find that when the pulse is stored in the dark Polariton field, there is an decrease in its amplitude with time due to the integral of the functions $A(t)$ & $C(t)$, which are in turn caused due to spontaneous emission and pulse broadening. The both factors restricts the time by which we can store the pulse inside the medium, as exceeding a definite timescale reduces the original pulse amplitude and eventually it gets lost. So in order to have a longer storage time we need to have $A(t)$ & $C(t)$ very small, which is only feasibly done by lowering the two photon dephasing rate of the probe laser Γ_{ba} .

Conclusion:

The optical storage by the non-linear optical processes like EIT has opened many doors. Recent experiments have been successful in storing pulse for nearly a minute. As research progresses we hope to cross even this number. Also the question is not only for the feasibility of longer storage it is also about the feasibility of the process itself to be utilized in modern quantum computers as EIT phenomenon is very difficult to obtain in laboratory, not to mention the expensiveness of the process. The efficiency of the entire storage device that we likely make a reality in the field of quantum mechanics has to pass these barriers.

Bibliography

- Standing Wave Electromagnetically Induced Transparency Kristian Rymann Hansen
QUANTOP Department of Physics and Astronomy University of Aarhus, Denmark
- Electromagnetically Induced Transparency by Joseph Scholle Advisor: Irina Novikov Senior
Research Coordinator: Henry Krakauer
- Electromagnetically Induced Transparency by Wesley W. Erickson
- Electromagnetically Induced Transparency: Optics in Coherent Media Michael Fleischhauer,
Atac Imamoglu, and Jonathan P. Marangos
- Stimulated hyper-Raman adiabatic passage. II. Static compensation of dynamic Stark Shifts
S. Gue'rin, L. P. Yatsenko, T. Halfmann, B. W. Shore, and K. Bergmann
- Density Matrix Formalism: Electromagnetically Induced Transparency in a Three-Level
Atomic System Jianping Hu, Subhankar Roy, and M. Ummal Momeen
- Electromagnetically Induced Transparency by J.P. Marangos & T. Halfmann
- Master Equation methods in Quantum Optics by G. S. Agarwal
- www.wikipedia.org
- www.google.com